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Research Article

**A COMPARATIVE RESEARCH ON DISABLED AND NON-
DISABLED CHILDREN'S MOTHERS IN TERMS OF
DEPRESSION AND ANXIETY PREVALENCE**¹Namra Tufail, ¹Shifa Batool, ²Dr. Atta ur Rehman¹Fatima Jinnah Medical University²Mohi-ud-Din Islamic Medical College, Mirpur, AJ & K.**Abstract:**

Objectives: Our research aimed at the depression and anxiety prevalence in the non-disableds and disabled children's mothers in the perspective of demographic features.

Method: We conducted a cross-sectional comparative research to distinguish variations in the depression and anxiety level of non-disableds and disabled children's mothers (n=340) with 170 mothers in each study group at Allied Hospital, Faisalabad (September, 2016 to October, 2017). We used HADS (Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale) for the depression and anxiety assessment of the subject sample and data analysis was carried out through SPSS and ANOVA.

Results: Statistically significant depression and anxiety was observed in the research population (P-value < 0.001). Anxiety was observed in the disabled children's mothers (78%). Non-disableds children's mothers were (52%). Depression was dominant in the mothers of disabled children than the non-disabled cases that is 46% versus 76%. There was a positive association between depression and anxiety with respect to mother and children age respectively observed as P-value as (< 0.05); whereas, an inverse relation was observed with mother's literacy and children age with a significant P-value of (< .01) including status of the family income.

Conclusion: Demands of the disabled children are better understood by mothers with the advancement in the children age which reduces anxiety. Psychologists may get assistance from the research outcomes in order to deal with the cases of disabled children's mothers related to depression and anxiety.

Key words: Depression, Anxiety and Disabled Children.

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INTRODUCTION:

Parents feel excited when new guest arrives in this world but disappointment is the fate with any disability at the time of birth. Feeling of guilt and complex is the result of disabled births. Globally 350 million already suffer these guilts [1]. Anxiety and depression is felt in West respectively 10% & 9% [2]. Higher disability rate is observed in Pakistani population (5.035 million) with respective division of physically disability, blindness, mental retarded, deaf and multiple disabilities with respective proportions of 19.2%, 8.2%, 7.6%, 7.5% and 8.3% [3]. Disability is dominant in the rural than urban areas. As Punjab is densely populated province so the disability is also higher in this province [4]. Negative impact has been produced by such studies and the prevalence of depression and anxiety is common in the mothers of disabled children [5 – 9].

Mothers responsibility is more than the fathers because of cultural and professional restrictions in Pakistan as men usually work for the livelihood. Societal stigma is also faced by the mothers. This conforms with the depression and anxiety generally in disabled children's parents specifically mothers [10, 11].

There is a variation in the parental depression reporting in various studies [12]. Higher anxiety is also reported in the parents with children being affected by autism and down syndrome including cerebral palsy [13 – 15]. Less stress is reported in the parents of blind and deaf children than the earlier mentioned cases [16, 17]. Disabilities are common in low social circles and variation in depression have been observed with the variation of variables such as socio-demographic features, family income, marital status, age, education etc.; limited sources are also a

hindrance is level of satisfaction which links with the socio-economic state [18 – 21].

Extension of services for these disabled children is challenging which requires expertise and special concern. Future of the special children is a hot issue for society and parents. Complete children care needs relaxed and contended mothers which is almost impossible as mothers have feelings for their toddlers. Therefore, we aimed at the depression and anxiety prevalence in the non-disabled and disabled children's mothers in the perspective of demographic features.

More depression and anxiety are faced by the mothers in case of disabled children, HADS score was above seven in the disabled children mothers than the non-disabled children. A reciprocal association was present in the mother and child age and income of the family with level of anxiety and depression.

METHOD PARTICIPANTS:

We conducted a cross-sectional comparative research to distinguish variations in the depression and anxiety level of non-disabled and disabled children's mothers (n=340) with 170 mothers in each study group at Allied Hospital, Faisalabad (September, 2016 to October, 2017). We used HADS (Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale) for the depression and anxiety assessment of the subject sample and data analysis was carried out through SPSS and ANOVA.

The sample of non-disabled children's mothers residing in the same geographical area with common demographic features such as (marital status, age range and education) have been reflected in (Table – I & II).

Table – I: Demographic characteristics of mothers

Mothers (170)		Number	Percentage
Age in Years	M (SD)	37.99 (5.93)	
	Range	25 – 45	
Level of Education	Uneducated	60	35.2
	Primary –Middle	75	44.11
	Matric – Intermediate	29	17.05
	Graduation – Post Graduation	6	3.5
Marital Status	Married	164	96.47
	Widow/ Divorced	6	3.5
Monthly Family Income	0 – 10000	93	54.7
	11000 – 20000	60	35.29
	21000 – 30000	12	7
	31000 – 40000	5	2.9
Family System	Nuclear	138	81.17
	Joint	32	18.82
Number of Children	One	8	4.7
	Two	15	8.82
	Three or more	147	86.47
Number of Disabled children	One	118	69.41
	Two or more	52	30.58

Table – II: Demographic characteristics of children with disability

Children (170)		Number	Percentage
Age in Years	M (SD)	11.21 (2.77)	
	Range	5 – 15	
Gender	Boys	104	61.17
	Girls	66	38.82
Type of Disability	Hearing Impaired	57	33.52
	Mentally Challenged	54	31.76
	Physically Disabled	38	22.35
	Visually Impaired	21	12.35
Level of Education	Nursery – KG-II	89	52.35
	One – Five	72	42.35
	Six – Eight	9	5.29
Birth Order	Eldest	54	31.76
	Middle	110	64.7
	Youngest	6	3.52

Basic demographics information was obtained through a questionnaire which included information about gender, type of disability, age, education level, no of children, birth order family monthly income, family system and marital status etc.

HADS is originally a self-developed instrument used to measure depression and anxiety level [22, 23]. Response categories are scored from zero to three as per the symptoms severity; depression and anxiety are scored from 0 – 21. HADS score is categorized as normal, mild, moderate and severe with respective numeric figures as (≤ 7), 8 – 10, 11 – 14 and 15 – 21 [13, 22, 24].

Willing mothers were interviewed during the counselling sessions with psychologist. Sessions were according to HADS questions, free and relax environment was maintained. We also approached the mothers of non-disables children and same procedure was adopted disabled children mothers.

RESULTS:

Statistically significant depression and anxiety was observed in the research population (P-value < 0.001). Anxiety was observed in the disable children's mothers (78%). Non-disables children's mothers were (52%). Depression was dominant in the mothers of disabled children than the non-disabled cases that is 46% versus 76%. There was a positive association between depression and anxiety with respect to mother and children age respectively observed as P-value as (< 0.05); whereas, an inverse relation was observed with mother's literacy and children age with a significant P-value of (< .01) including status of the family income. Detailed outcomes on demographic features, disabled children and HADS depression and anxiety through ANCOVA analysis have been respectively shown in Table I, II and III.

Table - III: ANCOVA Analysis of ‘Anxiety and Depression on HADS’ Scores for Mothers of Disabled and Non-disabled Children

Mother of Disables Child (170)			Mother of Non-Disabled Child (170)			
Scales	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	F	P-Value
Anxiety	10.7	3.79	8.11	3.45	32.41	0.001
Depression	9.98	3.49	7.31	3.07	42.26	0.001

DISCUSSION:

We determined mother's mental health in both disabled and non-disabled children's mothers. We studied that how the overall well-being of the mothers is affected by depression and anxiety caused by the effects of disability. Non-disabled and disabled children's mothers were compared in this comparative research with additional demographic exploration of both the groups. More anxiety and depression were prevalent in the disabled children group than the non-disabled in the controlled family income and education. Our outcomes can be compared with two other authors in terms of depression and anxiety prevalence conducted in various settings [25, 26].

In the brought up of a disabled child mothers do face psychological distress such as depression and anxiety in the presence of any disability [10]. Mothers are vulnerable to these psychological distresses as they are more involved in the bringing of a child [6].

Outcomes of our research report that anxiety was found in (78%) of disabled children's mothers; whereas, various depression degrees were observed in (76%). Our region of South Asia is observed with higher prevalence of depression and anxiety than the other regions in the global perspective [1]. The outcomes of our research can be compared with the outcomes as referred in the references list and there are concerns in the parents about the future life of the disabled child and about his community living [27, 28].

Social and economic burden have been shared in the research of another author in terms of family routine disturbance and intellectual disability as the survival of a disabled individual in the society is very painful and it is even higher than the death of non-disabled child [9, 29, 30]. We also explored depression and anxiety literature in both the groups regarding demographic features. Outcomes reflect that positive

association was present in the age of the mother with depression and anxiety which was same as reported in another research of same kind [27]. Inverse relation was established with the education of the mother in terms of depression and anxiety which can be conformed with other studies as well [14, 31]. Insight is increased in the mothers after being educated and aware about severity than the non-educated mothers. Appropriate resource selection is also easy for the educated mothers than the non-educated mothers to rehabilitate their children.

Family income had also an inverse relation with the depression and anxiety which is also confirmed by others studies [12, 30]. Pakistani healthcare system extends free services for the disabled children but these facilities are very meager than required as low level of the society suffers a lot as they need to travel much to be facilitated by these facilities. At the end, there was a tiny association of disabled children age with depression and anxiety of the mothers as children grew old it is easier for the mothers to understand their needs and requirements and management becomes a bit simple and relaxing for the mothers. Similarly, there was no variation in the parenting stress in the school going children having autism [32].

CONCLUSION:

We may conclude as mothers are more prone to depression and anxiety than fathers in the disabled children case. Depression and anxiety prevalence was 76% and 78% respectively in the disabled children's mothers group; whereas, in the non-disabled children's mothers group depression and anxiety stand at 48% and 53% respectively. Family income, mother education, child age is in inverse relation to depression and anxiety; whereas, the age of the mother has a positive association with the depression and anxiety.

REFERENCES:

1. Gupta R. K., and Kaur, H. Stress among parents of children with intellectual disability. *Asia Pacific Disability Rehabilitation Journal*, 2010; 21 (2): 618 – 625.
2. Seshadri, M. K., Verma, S. K., and Prashad. Impact of mental retardation of child on the family in India. *Journal of Clinical Psychology*, 2000; 11: 473 – 498.
3. Lawoko, S., and Soares, J. J. Quality of life among parents of children with congenital heart disease, parents of children with other diseases and parents of healthy children. *Quality Life Research*, 2003; 12: 655 – 666.
4. Mirzamani, M., Ashoori, M., and Sereshki, N. A. The effect of social and token economy reinforcements on academic achievement of students with intellectual disabilities. *Iranian Journal of Psychiatry*, 2011; 6 (1): 25 – 30.
5. Lai, F. J. The relationships between parenting stress, child characteristics, parenting self-efficacy, and social support in parents of children with autism in Taiwan (Doctoral thesis, Columbia University), 2013: P.20582.
6. Olsson, M. B., and Hwang, P. H. Depression in mothers and fathers of children with intellectually disability. *Journal of Intellectual Disability Research*, 2001; 45(6): 535-543.
7. Abasiubong, F., Obembe, A., and Ekpo, M. A controlled study of anxiety and depression in mothers of children with learning disability in Lagos, Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Medicine*, 2006; 15 (2): 124-127.
8. Hastings, R. P. Child behavior problems and partner mental health as correlates of stress in mothers and fathers of children with autism. *Journal of Intellectual Disability Research*, 2003; 47 (4): 231 – 237.
9. Marika, V. Depression symptoms and emotional states in parents of disabled and non-disabled children. *Social Behavior and Personality: An International Journal*, 1999; 27 (1): 87 – 97.
10. Bumin, G., Günal, A., and Tükel, P. Anxiety, depression and quality of life in mothers of disabled children. *ARAP TIRMA*, 2008; 15 (1): 6 – 11.
11. Sousa, D. E. Mothers of children with developmental disabilities: An analysis of psychopathology. *Journal of Pakistan Psychiatric Society*, 2010; 7 (2): 84 – 87.
12. Anjum, N., and Malik, F. Parenting practices in mothers of children with ADHD: Role of stress and behavioral problems in children. *Pakistan Journal of Social and Clinical Psychology*, 2010; 8 (1): 18 – 38.
13. Fatima, I. and Suhail, K. Belief in a just world and subjective well-being: Mothers of normal and Down Syndromes children. *International Journal of Psychology*, 2010; 45 (6): 461 – 468.
14. Rezendes, D. L., and Scarpa, A. Association between parental anxiety / depression and child behavior problems related to autism spectrum disorders: The roles of parenting stress and parenting self-efficacy. *Autism Research and Treatment*, 2011; 20 (11): 1067 – 1077.
15. Sousa, A. D., and Singhvi, S. Depressive symptoms in mothers of children with cerebral palsy. *Journal of Pakistan Psychiatric Society*, 2011; 8 (1): 18 – 25.

16. Milian, M. Multicultural issues. In A. J. Koenig and M.C. Holbrook (Eds.). *Foundations of education: Instructional strategies for teaching children and youths with visual impairments*. New York: AFB Press, 2000; Vol.1, pp. 197 – 217.
17. Prakash, S. S., Prakash, S. G. R., Ravichandran, A., Susan, K. Y., and Alex, W. Measuring levels of stress and depression in mothers of children using hearing aids and cochlear implants: A comparative study. *International Journal of Special Education*, 2013; 28 (1):115 – 124.
18. Keller, D., and Honig, A. S. Maternal and paternal stress in families with school – age children with disabilities. *American Journal of Orthopsychiatry*, 2004;74: 337 – 348.
19. Blacher J. and Lopez S. Contributions to depression in Latina mothers with and without children with retardation: Implications for care – giving. *Family Relations: Interdisciplinary Journal of Applied Family Studies*,1997; 46: 325 – 34.
20. Hoare, P., Harris, M., Jackson, P., and Kerley, S. A community survey of children with severe intellectual disability and their families: psychological adjustment, career distress and the effect of respite care. *Journal of Intellectual Disability Research*, 1998; 42: 218 – 27.
21. Breslau N., Staruch K. S., Mortimer E. A. Psychological distress in mothers of disabled children. *American Journal of Diseases of Children*, 1982; 136: 682 – 6.
22. Zigmond, A. S., and Snaith, R. P. The Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale. *Acta Psychiatrica Scandinanica*,1983; 67: 361 – 370.
23. Mumford, D. B., Tareen, I. A. K., Bajwa, M. A. Z., Bhatti, M. R., and Karim, R. Translation and evaluation of an Urdu version of Hospital Anxiety and Depression Scale. *Acta Psychiatrica Scandinanica*, 1991; 83: 81 –85.
24. Suhail, K. Reliability analysis of the HAD scale across different cultural and ethnic groups. *Indian Journal of Clinical Psychology*, 2000; 27: 118 – 123.
25. Lakshmi, N., and Jabeen, Z. A study on parental anxiety among visually impaired and normal children. *IndianStreams Research Journal*, 2012; 113: 193 – 196.
26. Majumdar, M., Pereira, Y. D. S., and Fernandes, J. Stress and anxiety in parents of mentally retarded children. *Indian Journal of Psychiatry*, 2005; 47 (3): 144 –147.
27. Motamedi, S. H., Seyednour, R., Noorikhajavi, M., & Afghah, S. A study in depression levels among mother of disabled children. *Iranian Rehabilitation Journal*,2007; 5 (5,6).
28. World Health Organization, sixty-fifth world assembly,2012.
29. Pedersen, T. Anxiety more common in the western world, depression in east, 2012.
30. Population Association of Pakistan, (2002). *Pakistan’s population: Statistical profile* Islamabad, 2002.
31. Helping Hand for Relief and Development, 2012. *Persons with disabilities (PWDs) statistics in Pakistan*, Islamabad: Agha Gee, 2012.
32. Diwan, S., Chovatiya, H., and Diwan, J. Depression and quality of life in mothers of children with cerebral palsy. *National Journal of Integrated Research in Medicine*,2011; 2 (4): 11 – 13.